

PERCEiVE

Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collEctions
through al and Virtual Experiences

a cultural
probe kit
on curiosity

activity book diary

for designers to explore and solicit
care in Cultural Heritage domain

This work is part of a research project conducted by CNR ISPC and the University of Bologna – DHDK (Interactive Media Design course). It has been further developed within the PERCEIVE project to explore and study “caring attitude” and its triggers in XR experiences.

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The authors agree to enable scholars to use it free of charge, quoting it as:

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My Cultural Probe Kit

Number __

Dear Friend, this is a kit made for you. It is called “Cultural Probe Kit” because it is used by designers to explore cultural behaviours and needs of their audience, in the creation of digital applications.

This particular Kit is meant to investigate how Curiosity works and how Curiosity could be used by Interactive Media.

It will be with you for the next 15 days. Please take care of it. It is composed by three parts.

We are a team of researchers of the National Research Council Institute of Heritage Science (CNR ISPC), and master students of DHDK at the University of Bologna.

Your contribution is anonymous; we ask you to NOT add your name and to SIGN here below, that you have read and agree with the instructions and with the potential use of the results for scientific publications, without any reference to personal indications.

Date

Signature

Instructions

This notebook is composed by 3 sections:

In the first, you'll be asked to complete daily tasks; In the second, you'll find a diary that will be with you for 7 days; the last contains more advanced tasks related to Cultural Heritage.

You won't need any previous experience nor particular technology, just a pen, your phone (to scan QRcodes and access online material), and some of your time.

Please fill this book in complete sincerity, it will be completely anonymous and you will not be judged for your answers.

When you have finished, please take pictures of every page and send them to this e-mail:

imd.dhdk.unibo@gmail.com

You have 15 days to finish all activities.

My Cultural Probe Kit

1: my Activity Book

Activity 1

Who am I?

Frame this QRcode with your phone and follow the link to answer to a few questions about you. If you prefer you can answer directly in this book.

Please Include here the number of your kit: _____

Year of Birth* _____

Nationality* _____

What is your last degree? (i.e. undergraduate, graduate, master, phd, etc.)*

In which field you took your last degree? (i.e. Humanities, Economics, etc.)

How often do you visit sites or Monuments?*

Never 1 2 3 4 5 Often

How often do you visit museums?*

Never 1 2 3 4 5 Often

How often do you visit temporary exhibitions?*

Never 1 2 3 4 5 Often

With whom do you visit sites or museums? *

Alone Friends Colleagues Family School
 Strangers in guided visits Other: _____

I would describe myself as someone who actively seeks as much information as I can in a new situation*

1 2 3 4 5
Completely disagree Totally agree

Everywhere I go, I am out looking for new things or experiences*

1 2 3 4 5
Completely disagree Totally agree

I enjoy learning about subjects that are unfamiliar to me*

1 2 3 4 5
Completely disagree Totally agree

I find it fascinating to learn new information*

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

When talking to someone, I try to discover interesting details about them. *

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

I am the kind of person who embraces unfamiliar people, events, and places. *

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

I can't stand when a television program ends with a cliffhanger*

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

I have a hard time accepting mysteries can't be solved*

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

Thinking about solutions to difficult conceptual problems can keep me awake at night.

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

I can spend hours on a single problem because I just can't rest without knowing the answer. *

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

I feel frustrated if I can't figure out the solution to a problem, so I work even harder to solve it. *

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

It bothers me if I don't know a word and I will look up the meaning*

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

If a word is on the tip of my tongue, it bothers me until I can think of it*

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

If I read something that doesn't make sense, I ignore it and keep reading*

1 2 3 4 5

Completely disagree Totally agree

I prefer friends who are excitingly unpredictable*

	1	2	3	4	5	
Completely disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Totally agree				

Creating an adventure as I go is much more appealing than a planned adventure*

	1	2	3	4	5	
Completely disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Totally agree				

I like to do things that are a little frightening*

	1	2	3	4	5	
Completely disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Totally agree				

Risk-taking is exciting to me*

	1	2	3	4	5	
Completely disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Totally agree				

I find it hard to explore new places when I lack confidence in my abilities*

	1	2	3	4	5	
Completely disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Totally agree				

I am at my best when doing something that is complex or challenging*

	1	2	3	4	5	
Completely disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Totally agree				

Activity 2

FEELING CURIOUS?

This space is here to host your thoughts and feelings regarding Curiosity. Please read the initial suggestion and feel free to write your stories and your life episodes, that would be treated anonymously (we will not know your name) and shared ONLY if you allow us to do so.

If you want to leave your email, it will be used to send your stories back to you.

Email *

Indirizzo email valido

When you have done take a picture of the paper or upload the PDF or Word file at this link:

Read again your story and reflect

What sparked your curiosity?

What did you do after?

Read again your story and reflect

Did your friend already know about it?

Ask your friend how curious he/she felt about your story (from 1 / not at all/ to 5 / very much):

1 2 3 4 5

What triggered his/her curiosity most?

What did you do to make your story more interesting?

Story Time (inspirations)

mic_italia Archeologia, nuove straordinarie statue in bronzo scoperte al santuario di San Casciano dei Bagni, dalle acque termali il rinvenimento più grande mai emerso in Italia, riscriverà la storia della statuaria etrusca-romana.

Il Ministro Sangiuliano: ritrovamento eccezionale, Italia ricca di tesori immensi e unici

Oltre 20 statue di bronzo in perfetto stato di conservazione, ex voto e altri oggetti. Sono le nuove scoperte restituite dalla campagna di scavo eseguita nel santuario etrusco-romano de @il_santuario_ritrovato_scb, in provincia di Siena. Iniziato nel 2019, lo scavo è stato promosso dal MiC e dal comune toscano e ha condotto agli straordinari ritrovamenti nelle prime settimane di ottobre.

museiunibo

Museo di Palazzo Poggi - SMA Unibo

112 likes

museiunibo 🌻 #SaveTheDate 🌸 Giovedì 8 dicembre 2022 aprirà al pubblico, presso il Museo di Palazzo Poggi, la mostra "L'ALTRO RINASCIMENTO. Ulisse Aldrovandi e le meraviglie del mondo".

🌿 Un'occasione unica per scoprire un episodio tanto importante quanto poco conosciuto del Rinascimento: il risveglio delle scienze naturali.

🌿 Un percorso espositivo tra arte e scienza, per comprendere come, da antichi, abbiamo cominciato ad essere moderni.

mondmostre
mondmostre • Original audio

922 likes

mondmostre The Civic Archaeological Museum in Bologna will host masterpieces from what is considered the world's largest gallery of ancient art – the Naples Archaeological Museum. The exhibition offers a new perspective to allow visitors to explore the tastes and values of a world that remains a source of endless fascination for us: more than 100 works that explore the society of the 1st century A.D. starting from the role of pictores to the most stunning frescoes that embellished the ancient Roman houses of Pompeii.

I Pittori di Pompei - Museo Civico Archeologico di Bologna
23 Sept 2022 - 19 Mar 2023

comunedibologna
Bologna, Italy

comunedibologna 🤔🤔🤔 Nelle notti di settembre (15-19) la facciata incompiuta della Basilica di San Petronio si illumina di colori e disegni sulle note di Rossini. Potremo vedere proiettati così i disegni mai realizzati per il rivestimento della facciata, opera dei più celebri architetti della storia, dal Palladio in poi.
[#bolognaestate](#) [@bolognafestivalofficial](#)

Activity 4

Observe and Reply

Have a look to this picture and read the caption.

Hercules Farnese, II d.C. – III d.C. (MANN). Discovered in the Baths of Caracalla (Rome) during the XVI century, the marble statue of Hercules Farnese depicts the greek hero in a moment of rest, leaning onto his club after his last labour.

Looking at this image of the Hercules Farnese and reading its caption what triggers your curiosity?

Read again this alternative caption:

Hercules Farnese, II d.C. – III d.C. (MANN). Marble statue of Hercules at rest, despite looking plain white, analysis have shown that his skin should have looked more "tanned", of a brownish color, his eyes dark brown and his hairs and beard painted with a reddish pigment.

In this new caption what triggers your curiosity?

Would you search for more information about it? If yes, what do you plan to do?

yes no

Activity 5

WHAT MAKES ME CURIOUS?

During these 15 days plan a visit to a monument, a museum or to an exhibition.

While visiting it, look for something you feel particularly curious about and take a picture of it. Then upload it on line at this [link](#).

Now, look again at your picture and reply.

What is the subject of your photo?

Why did you decide to photograph it?

Why were you curious about it?

Activity 6

PROF. FOR A DAY

Choose a day of your week, when you have lessons (any day could be perfect for this task). When you come back from the lessons, please complete these questions.

Were you **CURIOUS** about any of the topic your professors talked about today? yes no

What was the topic about?

Why did you feel curious about it?

Was there a topic you found **BORING** or particularly indifferent today? yes no

What was it about?

If you had to teach that same topic to one of your friends, how could you make it more interesting?

Activity 7

YOUR TURN TO ASK QUESTIONS (1/2)

Today, you are going to interview one component of your FAMILY. Ask him/her to tell you about a situation in which he/she felt particularly **CURIOUS about something, then summarize it here:**

Thanks for your contribution!

Now that you have finished, you can take the Activity Book back to the researcher or assistant who gave it to you, or you can keep it, if you like.

In this case, we ask you to take pictures or scan every page and send it to imd.dhdk.unibo@gmail.com

My Cultural Probe Kit

2: my Diary

Number ____

Starting Date _____

Dear Friend, this little diary will be with you for the next 8 days. Please take care of it. It is the second part of you “cultural probe kit”. It is used by designers to explore behaviours and needs of their audience.

It will be a way also for you to reflect on your life and on concepts such as “curiosity” and on the role of interactive technologies.

We are a team of researchers of the National Research Council Institute of Heritage Science (CNR ISPC), and a group of students of the master DHDK at the University of Bologna.

Your contribution will be anonymous; we ask you to NOT add your name and to sign that you have read and agree with the instructions and with the potential use of the results for scientific publications, without any reference to personal indications.

Date

Signature

Diary Instructions

This diary is the second part of your Cultural Probe Kit. You are going to fill in and complete it after part one (Activity Book). It is going to help you in focusing and reflecting. Every day, possibly before going to sleep, you are invited to think about your day, following suggestions about social cohesion. Write everything sincerely, in these pages. Your diary is anonymous, and we will respect your ideas and privacy.

You have 8 days to complete the diary

When you have finished, you can take it back to the researcher or assistant who gave it to you, or you can keep it, if you like. In this case we ask you to take pictures or scan every page and send it to imd.dhdk.unibo@gmail.com

Date: _____

DAY 1

Did I SEE something that captured my curiosity today? yes no

What was it? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Write a list of the 3 things that have most made you feel curious today:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Have I HEARD something that have captured my curiosity? yes no

What was it about? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Are you going to search for more information or investigate into some of the things that made you curious today? yes no

What? _____

Why? _____

My curiosity level today was: 1|2|3|4|5

Date: _____

DAY 2

Did I SEE something that captured my curiosity today? yes no

What was it? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Write a list of the 3 things that have most made you feel curious today:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Have I HEARD something that have captured my curiosity? yes no

What was it about? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Are you going to search for more information or investigate into some of the things that made you curious today? yes no

What? _____

Why? _____

My curiosity level today was: 1|2|3|4|5

Date: _____

DAY 3

Did I SEE something that captured my curiosity today? yes no

What was it? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Write a list of the 3 things that have most made you feel curious today:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Have I HEARD something that have captured my curiosity? yes no

What was it about? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Are you going to search for more information or investigate into some of the things that made you curious today? yes no

What? _____

Why? _____

My curiosity level today was: 1|2|3|4|5

Date: _____

DAY 4

Did I SEE something that captured my curiosity today? yes no

What was it? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Write a list of the 3 things that have most made you feel curious today:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Have I HEARD something that have captured my curiosity? yes no

What was it about? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Are you going to search for more information or investigate into some of the things that made you curious today? yes no

What? _____

Why? _____

My curiosity level today was: 1|2|3|4|5

Date: _____

DAY 5

Did I SEE something that captured my curiosity today? yes no

What was it? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Write a list of the 3 things that have most made you feel curious today:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Have I HEARD something that have captured my curiosity? yes no

What was it about? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Are you going to search for more information or investigate into some of the things that made you curious today? yes no

What? _____

Why? _____

My curiosity level today was: 1|2|3|4|5

Date: _____

DAY 6

Did I SEE something that captured my curiosity today? yes no

What was it? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Write a list of the 3 things that have most made you feel curious today:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Have I HEARD something that have captured my curiosity? yes no

What was it about? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Are you going to search for more information or investigate into some of the things that made you curious today? yes no

What? _____

Why? _____

My curiosity level today was: 1|2|3|4|5

Date: _____

DAY 7

Did I SEE something that captured my curiosity today? yes no

What was it? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Write a list of the 3 things that have most made you feel curious today:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Have I HEARD something that have captured my curiosity? yes no

What was it about? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Are you going to search for more information or investigate into some of the things that made you curious today? yes no

What? _____

Why? _____

My curiosity level today was: 1|2|3|4|5

Date: _____

DAY 8

Did I SEE something that captured my curiosity today? yes no

What was it? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Write a list of the 3 things that have most made you feel curious today:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Have I HEARD something that have captured my curiosity? yes no

What was it about? _____

Why were you curious about it?

Are you going to search for more information or investigate into some of the things that made you curious today? yes no

What? _____

Why? _____

My curiosity level today was: 1|2|3|4|5

Thanks for your contribution!

Now that you have finished, you can take the diary back to the researcher or assistant who gave it to you, or you can keep it, if you like.

In this case, we ask you to take pictures or scan every page and send it to imd.dhdk.unibo@gmail.com

My Cultural Probe Kit

3: my Activity Book
Lost Colours

Number ____

Activity 8

RESTORE THE LOST COLORS

Scanning the following [QRcode](#) you'll see a drawing made by a French author in the 19th century, of what he thought the inside of the Greek temple of Olympia could have looked like, with columns, marble floors, decors and the massive statue of Zeus in its centre.

Reproduction of the inside of the temple of Olympia

However, the original colors of the drawing have now faded away and we ask you to help us in restoring them. Proceed with the [link](#). You can also reply directly in the next pages.

The original drawing had colours that are now faded away, look at the following possible reconstructions and select which one you think could be the closest to the original.

A B C D E

Why do you think it could have looked like the option you chose? Did you do any researches?

To verify the correct answer, check on line.

Activity 9

Today we have a number of new technologies to identify traces of colour on ancient sculptures. Scan this [QRcode](#) and look at the experience of a team of researchers at the Museum of Fine Art of Boston with the analysis of polychromy in a replica of the Athena Parthenos, then answer to some additional task.

In 2020, the Museum of Fine Art of Boston started working on the opening of a new gallery dedicated to the cult of ancient Greek and Roman gods, however while setting up the gallery the team realized the first thing a visitor would notice stepping inside would have been a whole bunch of white marble sculptures, and that was not what the ancients would have seen at their time: they were in fact observing and praying their gods in colour, in their coloured statues. They started looking for traces of lost colours in the statue of their collections, and they reached some spectacular results.

Read about their discoveries in the following report, prepared by one of the researchers in the team.

Athena Parthenos - Polychromy Analysis - MFA Boston

"The first step was to just look at the statues with the bare eyes, very carefully, and soon we found that the roman statue of Athena Parthenos had quite a few traces of polychromy, fairly easily visible to the naked eye, especially looking at the locks and hair on her shoulder, where one could still see red paint: the Athena Parthenos was the perfect candidate for our study.

I started just with an hand magnifying glass and I really quickly but systematically surveyed at a large scale the whole sculpture. I then went on to set up a huge tripod that allowed me precise vertical and horizontal movement with a 50mm macro lens camera on top connected to a tethering software, that granted me the possibility of really see the marble surface of the statue, then, wherever I detected any possible traces of pigments, I further investigated them using a Dino-Lite hand microscope.

Through this first analysis we discovered a lot of yellow and yellow okra traces around Athena's ears, some brown under her toes used for the recesses of her sandals, and some grey paint inside the drill holes around the goddess' breastplate.

Second round of analysis was focused on the use of multispectral imaging. We used UV visible luminescence, infrared reflectography and visible induced luminescence (VIL), unfortunately the first two produced no results, however we were luckier with VIL exams.

VIL showed the presence of white pigments inside the eyes of the statue and blue pigments both mixed with the grey of the breastplate and in a very thick layer on the head of the statue, forming a very peculiar blue "unibrow" on top of Athena's eyes.

Comparing the results with other roman portrait of the same period we realized that the blue must have been either an underlayer used as a shadow or probably just a first base layer that would have been mixed with yellow okra to reach some sort of brown."

After reading this report rate your level of curiosity:*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

If you would have to tell the same story to one of your friends, what would you do to make it more interesting?*

What questions would you ask the team of researchers if you could talk to them?*

Scan & Watch

The same researchers also produced a brief video explaining the processes they followed and the results they obtained, please watch it and then answer to some last questions.

Athena reveals her true colors MFA Boston

After watching the video, rate your level of curiosity regarding this discovery*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

What are the aspects of this story that sparked your curiosity and caught your interest? Why?

Activity 10

WHY WHITE?

If indeed sculptures were polychrome, which were the processes that caused them to reach us without any color, or just mere traces, remaining?

Scan this [QRcode](#), think and reply.

What do you think may have happened during the centuries for statues to have lost their colors?

How much interested would you be in knowing more about this topic?*

Not interested at all Indifferent Very interested

Thanks for your contribution!

Now that you have finished, you can take the last task of the Activity Book back to the researcher or assistant who gave it to you, or you can keep it, if you like.

In this case, we ask you to take pictures or scan every page and send it to imd.dhdk.unibo@gmail.com

My Cultural Probe Kit

4: Activity with Colours at the museum

Number ____

Starting Date _____

Activity 11

EXPERT & CURIOSITY ROOM

Instructions for participant

This last activity is organised by a moderator and agreed with you about date and time you are available. It will require only between 30 min and 1 hour of your time.

You will meet experts, curators and scientists at the museum or in the laboratory; you will be involved with other people in an activity meant to make you curious about coloured collections and science.

Don't worry if you don't have previous knowledge, the final goal is to involve you, understand what trigger your curiosity, making you reflecting on the original colours of artworks.

Write an e-mail or contact the assistant who gave you this booklet and arrange a meeting.

After the activity has been carried out proceed and reply.

EXPERT & CURIOSITY ROOM

Instructions for designers

While researchers are working on the digitization and diagnostic analysis of polychrome Roman statues or of other Coloured artworks at the museum or in the laboratory, small groups of 3 to 5 visitors are allowed into the room to get a glimpse of what the experts are doing, guided by a moderator, in charge of a free 15-minute guided tour.

All guided tours follow the same structure:

1. Introduction on the ongoing PERCEIVE research and objectives
2. Introduction on digital acquisition (photogrammetric acquisition and preprocessing)
3. Focus on diagnostic analysis (imaging techniques – i.e. VIL and UVL -, first results and hints on other analysis)
4. Conclusion about approaches followed to make hypothesis on colour reconstruction and simulation

Thanks for having attended to the Expert & Curiosity Room Activity

Take some time and Summarize the experience you have just participated in, focusing on the aspects you considered more relevant according to your personal experience:

Please answer to these last questions

Did you know prior to this visit that Roman sculptures were polychrome? YES NO

If yes, how would you define your previous level of knowledge on the topic?

EXPERT PROFESSIONAL INTERESTED CURIOUS NEOPHYTE

How would you rate your level of curiosity towards the topic of polychromy after this visit (from 1: Not Curious at all; to 10: Extremely Curious)?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

What aspects of the research on polychromy were you mainly curious about? Why?

Do you think you would look for more information on polychromy after this visit? What would you plan on doing?

Quote this publication as:

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